

Appendix A

Modelling the Tennessee Eastman Process

Figure A.0.1 shows the architecture of the Tennessee Eastman challenge process. A first principles model of the process is given by Jockenhovel et al. (2004). This first principles model is the basis for a structural model of the process, and hence an adjacency matrix A_{TE} . The matrix A_{TE} calculates the digraph G_{TE} , and is detailed in the Matlab code xxx at the website xxx. The tables A.0.1 and A.1.1 show the model nomenclature.

Table A.0.1: Process equipment nomenclature for the Tennessee Eastman level 1 fusion model

Fig. A.0.1	Thesis	Type	Fig. A.0.1	Thesis	Type
v_1	FI1	Flow instrument	v_{20}	J120	Compressor work
v_2	FI2	Flow instrument	v_{21}	TI21	Temperature instrument
v_3	FI3	Flow instrument	v_{22}	TI13	Temperature instrument
v_4	FI4	Flow instrument	v_{23}	XI11g	Analyser
v_5	FI5	Flow instrument	v_{24}	XI11h	Analyser
v_6	FI6	Flow instrument	v_{25}	CV2	Control valve
v_7	PI7	Pressure instrument	v_{26}	CV3	Control valve
v_8	LI8	Level instrument	v_{27}	CV1	Control valve
v_9	TI9	Temperature instrument	v_{28}	CV4	Control valve
v_{10}	FI10	Flow instrument	v_{29}	CV8	Control valve
v_{11}	TI11	Temperature instrument	v_{30}	CV9	Control valve
v_{12}	LI12	Level instrument	v_{31}	CV10	Control valve
v_{13}	PI13	Pressure instrument	v_{32}	CV11	Control valve
v_{14}	FI14	Flow instrument	v_{33}	CV33	Control valve
v_{15}	LI15	Level instrument	v_{34}	CV34	Control valve
v_{18}	TI18	Temperature instrument	v_{35}	CV35	Control valve
v_{19}	FI19	Temperature instrument	LC7(Stripper)	LC31	Level controller
			LC7(Separator)	LC32	Level controller

Figure A.0.1: Tennessee Eastman Challenge process diagram. Reproduced from Luo et al. (2017) with permission. The two controllers LC7 are marked with boxes.

A.1 Description of the Process

The following description of the process is abbreviated from those presented in Jockenhovel et al., and Cameron and Gani (2011).

- i A mixer. The reactant feed streams 1,2,and 3 are mixed with the stripper vapour stream 5 and recycle stream 8 to yield stream 6. Stream 6 is fed into the reactor.
- ii A reactor. The reactor contains vapour and liquid phases in equilibrium. The overall reaction scheme is exothermic and excess heat is removed by cooling water. The feed and product streams of the reactor are vapour.
- iii A condenser. The vapour product stream 13 from the reactor is condensed by a water cooled condenser. The condensate is then fed to the separator. Jockenhovel et al. model the condenser as part of the separator. In effect, the reactor vapour stream 13 is assumed to be fed directly into the separator.
- iv A separator. The vapour-liquid equilibrium in the separator partitions the feed from the reactor into a vapour phase “tops”, and a liquid phase “bottoms”. The separator tops are split between purge stream 9, and a recycle stream through a compressor. The separator bottoms are fed into the stripper as stream 10.
- v A reactive steam stripper. The stripper is fed by liquid stream 10 from the separator and vapour phase reactant from stream 4. The stripper bottoms comprise liquid product stream 11. The stripper tops comprise vapour stream 5, and are fed into the mixer.
- vi A compressor. The partial flow from the separator tops that does not go into purge stream 9 is compressed and fed into the mixer. Jockenhovel et al, and Cameron and Gani do not model the compressor. In order to properly analyse the results of Chiang et al. (2015), this thesis introduces a simple compressor model based on a polytropic process.
- vii A balance of process devices. Besides these unit operations, the process includes controllers, instruments and analysers, and valves.

Level 1 structural models for the process are now presented, derived from Jockenhovel et al. (2004).

Table A.1.1: Nomenclature for the Tennessee Eastman level 1 fusion model.

Description	Variable	Example	Function	Example
Process chemical species	a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h	-	-	-
Vapour/liquid equilibrium coefficient for species i	ϕ_i	ϕ_a	-	-
Molar flow rate of stream i (Valve controlled)	q_i	q_4	Q_{CVi}	Q_{CV4}
Molar flow rate of stream i (Mass balance)	q_i	q_5	Q_i	Q_5
Number of moles of species i in unit operation j	n_{ij}	n_{aM}	N_{ij}	N_{aM}
Partial pressure of species i in unit operation j	p_{ij}	p_{aS}	P_{ij}	P_{aS}
Liquid mole fraction of species i in stream/unit operation j	χ_{ij}	χ_{dR}, χ_{d10}	X_{ij}	X_{dR}, X_{d10}
Vapour mole fraction of species i in stream/unit operation j	γ_{ij}	γ_{a6}	Γ_{ij}	Γ_{a6}
Energy generation rate of reaction r_i	e_{ri}	e_{r1}	E_{ri}	E_{r1}
Temperature of unit operation j	θ_j	θ_R	Θ_j	Θ_R
Heat transfer to / from unit operation j	h_j	h_R	H_j	H_R
Analyser for stream j, species k	y_{XIjk}	y_{XI6a}	Y_{XIjk}	Y_{XI6a}
Controller setpoint	r	r_{XC13}	-	-
Device malfunction	k	k_{FC1}	-	-
Flow controller, number N	y_{FCN}	y_{FC1}	Y_{FCN}	Y_{FC1}
Level controller, number N	y_{LCN}	y_{LC17}	Y_{LCN}	Y_{LC17}
Temperature controller, number N	y_{TCN}	y_{TC19}	Y_{TCN}	Y_{TC19}
Composition controller, number N	y_{XCN}	y_{XC13}	Y_{XCN}	Y_{XC13}

A.2 Control and Instrumentation Structural Modelling

A.2.1 Analyser modelling

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_{XI6a} &= Y_{XI6a}(\gamma_{a6}), y_{XC13} = Y_{XC13}(y_{XI6a}) \\
 y_{XI6d} &= Y_{XI6d}(\gamma_{d6}), y_{XC14} = Y_{XC14}(y_{XI6d}) \\
 y_{XI6e} &= Y_{XI6e}(\gamma_{e6}), y_{XC15} = Y_{XC15}(y_{XI6e}) \\
 y_{XI9a} &= Y_{XI9a}(\gamma_{b9}) \\
 y_{XI9b} &= Y_{XI9b}(\gamma_{b9}), y_{XC19} = Y_{XC19}(y_{XI9b}) \\
 y_{XI11e} &= Y_{XI11e}(\gamma_{e11}), y_{XC20} = Y_{XC20}(y_{XI11e})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.2.1}$$

A.2.2 FC3 control loop

$$y_{FI1} = Y_{FI1}(q_1), y_{FC3} = Y_{FC3}(y_{FI1}, y_{XC13}), q_1 = Q_{CV1}(y_{FC3}, k_{CV1}) \tag{A.2.2}$$

A.2.3 FC1 control loop

$$y_{FI2} = Y_{FI2}(q_2), y_{FC1} = Y_{FC1}(y_{FI2}, y_{XC14}), q_2 = Q_{CV2}(y_{FC1}, k_{CV2}) \quad (\text{A.2.3})$$

A.2.4 FC2 control loop

$$y_{FI3} = Y_{FI3}(q_3), y_{FC2} = Y_{FC2}(y_{FI3}, y_{XC15}), q_3 = Q_{CV3}(y_{FC2}, k_{CV3}) \quad (\text{A.2.4})$$

A.2.5 LC17 control loop

$$\begin{aligned} y_{LI8} &= Y_{LI8}(l_R), y_{LC17} = Y_{LC17}(y_{LI8}) \\ y_{FI4} &= Y_{FI4}(q_4), y_{FC4} = Y_{FC4}(q_{FI4}, y_{LC17}), q_4 = Q_{CV4}(y_{FC4}, k_{CV4}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2.5})$$

A.2.6 TC18 control loop

$$\begin{aligned} y_{TI9} &= Y_{TI9}(\theta_R), y_{TC18} = Y_{TC18}(y_{TI9}), y_{TC10} = Y_{TC10}(y_{TC18}, y_{TI21}) \\ y_{TI21} &= Y_{TI21}(\theta_{12o}), q_{12} = Q_{12}(y_{TC10}, k_{CV12}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2.6})$$

A.2.7 FC11 control loop

$$\begin{aligned} y_{FI17} &= Y_{FI17}(q_{11}), y_{FC11} = Y_{FC11}(y_{FI17}), q_{13} = Q_{CV13}(y_{FC11}, k_{CV13}) \\ y_{TI22} &= Y_{TI22}(\theta_{13o}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2.7})$$

A.2.8 Stream 6 flow indication

$$y_{FI6} = Y_{FI6}(q_6), d_{FI6} = D_{FI6}(y_{FI6}) \quad (\text{A.2.8})$$

A.2.9 Reactor pressure indication

$$y_{PI7} = Y_{PI7}(p_R), d_{PI7} = D_{PI7}(y_{PI7}) \quad (\text{A.2.9})$$

A.2.10 LC7 control loop

$$y_{LI15} = Y_{LI15}(l_P), y_{LC7} = Y_{LC7}(y_{LI15}), q_{11} = Q_{CV11}(y_{LC7}) \quad (\text{A.2.10})$$

A.2.11 FC9 control loop

$$y_{FI19} = Y_{FI19}(q_{33}), y_{FC9} = Y_{FC9}(y_{FI19}, y_{TC16}), q_{33} = Q_{CV33}(y_{FC9}) \quad (\text{A.2.11})$$

A.2.12 TC16 control loop

$$y_{TI18} = Y_{TI18}(\theta_P), y_{TC16} = Y_{TC16}(y_{TI18}, y_{XC20}) \quad (\text{A.2.12})$$

A.2.13 LC31 control loop

$$y_{LI12} = Y_{LI12}(l_S), y_{LC31} = Y_{LC31}(y_{LI12}), q_{10} = Q_{CV10}(y_{LC31}), y_{FI14} = Y_{FI14}(q_{10}) \quad (\text{A.2.13})$$

A.2.14 Separator temperature indication

$$y_{TI11} = Y_{TI11}(\theta_S) \quad (\text{A.2.14})$$

A.2.15 FC5 control loop

$$y_{FI5} = Y_{FI5}(q_8), y_{FC5} = Y_{FC5}(y_{FI5}), y_{FC5} = Y_{FC5}(y_{FI5}), q_{29} = Q_{CV29}(y_{FC5}) \quad (\text{A.2.15})$$

A.2.16 FC6 control loop

$$y_{FI10} = Y_{FI10}(q_9), y_{FC6} = Y_{FC6}(y_{FI10}, y_{XC19}), y_{PI13} = Y_{PI13}(p_S), y_{PHL6} = Y_{PHL6}(y_{PI13}) \\ q_9 = Q_9(y_{FC6}, y_{PHL6}) \quad (\text{A.2.16})$$

A.2.17 Stripper pressure indication

$$y_{PI16} = Y_{PI16}(p_P) \quad (\text{A.2.17})$$

A.2.18 Additional modelling

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_R &= L_R(n_{aR}, n_{bR}, n_{cR}, n_{dR}, n_{eR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}) \\
 l_S &= L_S(v_{IS}) \\
 w_C &= W_C(p_S), y_{II} = Y_{II}(w_C)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.2.18}$$

A.2.19 Detector modelling

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_{FI1} &= D_{FI1}(y_{FI1}), d_{FI2} = D_{FI2}(y_{FI3}), d_{FI3} = D_{FI3}(y_{FI3}), d_{FI4} = D_{FI4}(y_{FI4}), d_{FI5} = D_{FI5}(y_{FI5}), \\
 d_{FI6} &= D_{FI6}(y_{FI6}), d_{FI10} = D_{FI10}(y_{FI10}), d_{FI14} = D_{FI14}(y_{FI14}), d_{FI17} = D_{FI17}(y_{FI17}), d_{FI19} = D_{FI19}(y_{FI19}) \\
 \\
 d_{PI7} &= D_{PI7}(y_{PI7}), d_{PI13} = D_{PI13}(y_{PI13}), d_{PI16} = D_{PI16}(y_{PI16}) \\
 \\
 d_{LI8} &= D_{LI8}(y_{LI8}), d_{LI12} = D_{LI12}(y_{LI12}), d_{LI15} = D_{LI15}(y_{LI15}) \\
 \\
 d_{TI9} &= D_{TI9}(y_{TI9}), d_{TI11} = D_{TI11}(y_{TI11}), d_{TI18} = D_{TI18}(y_{TI18}), d_{TI21} = D_{TI21}(y_{TI21}), d_{TI22} = D_{TI22}(y_{TI22}) \\
 \\
 d_{II} &= D_{II}(y_{II}) \\
 \\
 d_{XI6a} &= D_{XI6a}(y_{XI6a}), d_{XI6d} = D_{XI6d}(y_{XI6d}), d_{XI6e} = D_{XI6e}(y_{XI6e}), d_{XI9a} = D_{XI9a}(y_{XI9a}), \\
 d_{XI9b} &= D_{XI9b}(y_{XI9b}), d_{XI11e} = D_{XI11e}(y_{XI11e})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.2.19}$$

A.3 Mixer Structural Modelling

A.3.1 Mixer mole balance

The model assumes that inert species B is associated with species A in streams 1 and 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_{aM} &= N_{aM}(\gamma_{a1}, q_1, \gamma_{a5}, q_5, \gamma_{a8}, q_8, \gamma_{a6}, q_6) \\
 n_{bM} &= N_{bM}(\gamma_{b1}, q_1, \gamma_{b5}, q_5, \gamma_{b8}, q_8, \gamma_{b6}, q_6) \\
 n_{cM} &= N_{cM}(\gamma_{c5}, q_5, \gamma_{c8}, q_8, \gamma_{c6}, q_6) \\
 n_{dM} &= N_{dM}(\gamma_{d2}, q_2, \gamma_{d5}, q_5, \gamma_{d8}, q_8, \gamma_{d6}, q_6) \\
 n_{eM} &= N_{eM}(\gamma_{e3}, q_3, \gamma_{e5}, q_5, \gamma_{e8}, q_8, \gamma_{e6}, q_6) \\
 n_{fM} &= N_{fM}(\gamma_{f5}, q_5, \gamma_{f8}, q_8, \gamma_{f6}, q_6) \\
 n_{gM} &= N_{gM}(\gamma_{g5}, q_5, \gamma_{g8}, q_8, \gamma_{g6}, q_6) \\
 n_{hM} &= N_{hM}(\gamma_{h5}, q_5, \gamma_{h8}, q_8, \gamma_{h6}, q_6)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.3.1}$$

A.3.2 Mixer energy balance

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_M &= \Theta_M(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}, \\
 &\quad q_1, q_2, q_3, q_5, q_8, \\
 &\quad \gamma_{a1}, \gamma_{a5}, \gamma_{a8}, \gamma_{b1}, \gamma_{b5}, \gamma_{b8}, \gamma_{c5}, \gamma_{c8}, \gamma_{d2}, \gamma_{d5}, \gamma_{d8}, \gamma_{e3}, \gamma_{e5}, \gamma_{e8}, \gamma_{f5}, \gamma_{f8}, \gamma_{g5}, \gamma_{g8}, \gamma_{h5}, \gamma_{h8}, \\
 &\quad \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_5, \theta_8)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.3.2}$$

A.3.3 Mixer pressure and vapour mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_M &= P_M(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}, v_M, \theta_M) \\
 \gamma_{a6} &= \Gamma_{a6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}), \gamma_{b6} = \Gamma_{b6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}) \\
 \gamma_{b6} &= \Gamma_{b6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}), \gamma_{d6} = \Gamma_{d6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}) \\
 \gamma_{e6} &= \Gamma_{e6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}), \gamma_{f6} = \Gamma_{f6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}) \\
 \gamma_{g6} &= \Gamma_{g6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM}), \gamma_{h6} = \Gamma_{h6}(n_{aM}, n_{bM}, n_{cM}, n_{dM}, n_{eM}, n_{fM}, n_{gM}, n_{hM})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.3.3}$$

A.4 Reactor Structural Modelling

A.4.1 Reactor mole balance

$$\begin{aligned}n_{aR} &= N_{aR}(\gamma_{a6}, q_6, \gamma_{a7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}), n_{bR} = N_{bR}(\gamma_{b6}, q_6, \gamma_{b7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}) \\n_{cR} &= N_{cR}(\gamma_{c6}, q_6, \gamma_{c7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}), n_{dR} = N_{dR}(\gamma_{d6}, q_6, \gamma_{d7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}) \\n_{eR} &= N_{eR}(\gamma_{e6}, q_6, \gamma_{e7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}), n_{fR} = N_{fR}(\gamma_{f6}, q_6, \gamma_{f7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}) \\n_{gR} &= N_{gR}(\gamma_{g6}, q_6, \gamma_{g7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3}), n_{hR} = N_{hR}(\gamma_{h6}, q_6, \gamma_{h7}, q_7, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3})\end{aligned}\tag{A.4.1}$$

A.4.2 Reactor energy balance

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_R &= \Theta_R(n_{aR}, n_{bR}, n_{cR}, n_{dR}, n_{eR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}, \\&\quad q_6, \gamma_{a6}, \gamma_{b6}, \gamma_{c6}, \gamma_{d6}, \gamma_{e6}, \gamma_{f6}, \gamma_{g6}, \gamma_{h6}, \\&\quad \theta_{12}, e_{r1}, e_{r2}, e_{r3}, k_{r1}, k_{r2}, k_{r3})\end{aligned}\tag{A.4.2}$$

A.4.3 Reaction enthalpies

$$e_{r1} = E_{r1}(\theta_R, q_1), e_{r2} = E_{r2}(\theta_R, q_2), e_{r3} = E_{r3}(\theta_R, q_3)\tag{A.4.3}$$

A.4.4 Reactor heat exchanger

$$\theta_{12} = \Theta_{12}(q_{12}, \theta_R, \theta_{12i}), \theta_{12o} = \Theta_{12o}(\theta_{12})\tag{A.4.4}$$

A.4.5 Reaction rates

$$\begin{aligned}k_{r1} &= K_{r1}(v_{vR}, p_{aR}, p_{cR}, p_{dR}, \theta_R) \\k_{r2} &= K_{r2}(v_{vR}, p_{aR}, p_{cR}, p_{dR}, \theta_R) \\k_{r3} &= K_{r3}(v_{vR}, p_{aR}, p_{cR}, p_{dR}, \theta_R)\end{aligned}\tag{A.4.5}$$

A.4.6 Reactor pressure

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_R &= P_R(p_{aR}, p_{bR}, p_{cR}, p_{dR}, p_{eR}, p_{fR}, p_{gR}, p_{hR}) \\
 p_{aR} &= P_{aR}(n_{aR}, \theta_R, v_{vR}), p_{bR} = P_{bR}(n_{bR}, \theta_R, v_{vR}), p_{cR} = P_{cR}(n_{cR}, \theta_R, v_{vR}) \\
 p_{dR} &= P_{dR}(x_{dR}, \theta_R), p_{eR} = P_{eR}(x_{eR}, \theta_R), p_{fR} = P_{fR}(x_{fR}, \theta_R) \\
 p_{gR} &= P_{gR}(x_{gR}, \theta_R), p_{hR} = P_{hR}(x_{hR}, \theta_R)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.4.6}$$

A.4.7 Reactor liquid mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{dR} &= X_{dR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}), x_{cR} = X_{cR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}), x_{fR} = X_{fR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}) \\
 x_{gR} &= X_{gR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}), x_{hR} = X_{hR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.4.7}$$

A.4.8 Reactor vapour mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_{aR} &= \Gamma_{aR}(p_{aR}, p_R), \gamma_{bR} = \Gamma_{bR}(p_{bR}, p_R), \gamma_{cR} = \Gamma_{cR}(p_{cR}, p_R), \gamma_{dR} = \Gamma_{dR}(p_{dR}, p_R) \\
 \gamma_{eR} &= \Gamma_{eR}(p_{eR}, p_R), \gamma_{fR} = \Gamma_{fR}(p_{fR}, p_R), \gamma_{gR} = \Gamma_{gR}(p_{gR}, p_R), \gamma_{hR} = \Gamma_{hR}(p_{hR}, p_R)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.4.8}$$

A.4.9 Reactor liquid volume

$$v_{lR} = V_{lR}(n_{dR}, n_{cR}, n_{fR}, n_{gR}, n_{hR}) \tag{A.4.9}$$

A.4.10 Reactor vapour volume

$$v_{vR} = V_{vR}(v_R, v_{lR}) \tag{A.4.10}$$

A.4.11 Stream 6 flow and stream 7 flow

$$q_6 = Q_6(p_M, p_R), q_7 = Q_7(p_R, p_S) \tag{A.4.11}$$

A.5 Separator Structural Modelling

A.5.1 Separator mole balance

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_{aS} &= N_{aS}(\gamma_{a7}, q_7, \gamma_{a8}, q_8, q_9), n_{bS} = N_{bS}(\gamma_{b7}, q_7, \gamma_{b8}, q_8, q_9), n_{cS} = N_{cS}(\gamma_{c7}, q_7, \gamma_{c8}, q_8, q_9) \\
 n_{dS} &= N_{dS}(\gamma_{d7}, q_7, \gamma_{d8}, q_8, q_9), n_{eS} = N_{eS}(\gamma_{e7}, q_7, \gamma_{e8}, q_8, q_9, x_{e10}, q_{10}) \\
 n_{fS} &= N_{fS}(\gamma_{f7}, q_7, \gamma_{f8}, q_8, q_9, x_{f10}, q_{10}), n_{gS} = N_{gS}(\gamma_{g7}, q_7, \gamma_{g8}, q_8, q_9, x_{g10}, q_{10}) \\
 n_{hS} &= N_{hS}(\gamma_{h7}, q_7, \gamma_{h8}, q_8, q_9, x_{h10}, q_{10})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.1}$$

A.5.2 Separator energy balance

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_S &= \Theta_S(n_{aS}, n_{bS}, n_{cS}, n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}, q_7, \gamma_{a7}, \gamma_{b7}, \gamma_{c7}, \gamma_{d7}, \gamma_{e7}, \gamma_{f7}, \gamma_{g7}, \gamma_{ha7}, \\
 &\quad \theta_R, \theta_{13}, h_{0S})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.2}$$

A.5.3 Stream 8 temperature

$$\theta_8 = \Theta_8(\theta_S, p_M, p_S) \tag{A.5.3}$$

A.5.4 Heat of vaporisation

$$h_{0S} = H_{0S}(q_{10}, x_{d10}, x_{e10}, x_{f10}, x_{g10}, x_{h10}) \tag{A.5.4}$$

A.5.5 Separator heat exchanger

$$\theta_{13} = \Theta_{13}(q_{13}, \theta_S, \theta_{13i}), \theta_{13o} = \Theta_{13o}(\theta_{13}) \tag{A.5.5}$$

A.5.6 Separator pressure

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_S &= P_S(p_{aS}, p_{bS}, p_{cS}, p_{dS}, p_{eS}, p_{fS}, p_{gS}, p_{hS}) \\
 p_{aS} &= P_{aS}(n_{aS}, \theta_S, v_{vS}), p_{bS} = P_{bS}(n_{bS}, \theta_S, v_{vS}), p_{cS} = P_{cS}(n_{cS}, \theta_S, v_{vS}) \\
 p_{dS} &= P_{dS}(x_{d10}, \theta_S, v_{vS}), p_{eS} = P_{eS}(x_{e10}, \theta_S, v_{vS}), p_{fS} = P_{fS}(x_{f10}, \theta_S, v_{vS}) \\
 p_{gS} &= P_{gS}(x_{g10}, \theta_S, v_{vS}), p_{hS} = P_{hS}(x_{h10}, \theta_S, v_{vS})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.6}$$

A.5.7 Stream 8 vapour mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_{a8} &= \Gamma_{a8}(p_{aS}, p_S), \gamma_{b8} = \Gamma_{b8}(p_{bS}, p_S), \gamma_{c8} = \Gamma_{c8}(p_{cS}, p_S), \gamma_{d8} = \Gamma_{d8}(p_{dS}, p_S) \\
 \gamma_{e8} &= \Gamma_{e8}(p_{eS}, p_S), \gamma_{f8} = \Gamma_{f8}(p_{fS}, p_S), \gamma_{g8} = \Gamma_{g8}(p_{gS}, p_S), \gamma_{h8} = \Gamma_{h8}(p_{hS}, p_S)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.7}$$

A.5.8 Stream 9 vapour mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_{a9} &= \Gamma_{a9}(p_{aS}, p_S), \gamma_{b9} = \Gamma_{b9}(p_{bS}, p_S), \gamma_{c9} = \Gamma_{c9}(p_{cS}, p_S), \gamma_{d9} = \Gamma_{d9}(p_{dS}, p_S) \\
 \gamma_{e9} &= \Gamma_{e9}(p_{eS}, p_S), \gamma_{f9} = \Gamma_{f9}(p_{fS}, p_S), \gamma_{g9} = \Gamma_{g9}(p_{gS}, p_S), \gamma_{h9} = \Gamma_{h9}(p_{hS}, p_S)
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.8}$$

A.5.9 Stream 10 liquid mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{d10} &= X_{d10}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}), x_{e10} = X_{e10}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}) \\
 x_{f10} &= X_{f10}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}), x_{g10} = X_{g10}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}) \\
 x_{h10} &= X_{h10}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS})
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.5.9}$$

A.5.10 Separator liquid and vapour volumes

$$v_{lS} = V_{lS}(n_{dS}, n_{eS}, n_{fS}, n_{gS}, n_{hS}, v_{vS} = V_{vS}(v_S, v_{lS})) \tag{A.5.10}$$

A.6 Stripper (Product) Structural Modelling

A.6.1 Stripper mole balance

$$n_{\text{gP}} = N_{\text{gP}}(x_{\text{g10}}, q_{10}, x_{\text{g11}}, q_{11}), n_{\text{hP}} = N_{\text{hP}}(x_{\text{h10}}, q_{10}, x_{\text{h11}}, q_{11}) \quad (\text{A.6.1})$$

A.6.2 Stripper energy balance

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\text{P}} &= \Theta_{\text{P}}(n_{\text{gP}}, n_{\text{hP}}, q_{10}, x_{\text{d10}}, x_{\text{e10}}, x_{\text{f10}}, x_{\text{g10}}, x_{\text{h10}}, \theta_{\text{S}}, q_4, \gamma_{\text{a4}}, \gamma_{\text{b4}}, \gamma_{\text{c4}}, \theta_4, h_{\text{P}}, h_{\text{OP}}) \\ h_{\text{OP}} &= H_{\text{OP}}(\gamma_{\text{d5}}, \gamma_{\text{e5}}, \gamma_{\text{f5}}, \gamma_{\text{g5}}, \gamma_{\text{h5}}, q_4, q_5), h_{\text{P}} = H_{\text{P}}(q_{33}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6.2})$$

A.6.3 Stripper volumes, liquid level, and pressure

$$v_{\text{IP}} = V_{\text{IP}}(n_{\text{gP}}, v_{\text{hP}}), l_{\text{P}} = L_{\text{P}}(v_{\text{IP}}), v_{\text{VP}} = V_{\text{VP}}(v_{\text{P}}, v_{\text{IP}}), p_{\text{P}} = P_{\text{P}}(v_{\text{VP}}, \theta_{\text{P}}) \quad (\text{A.6.3})$$

A.6.4 Stripper vapour-liquid equilibrium

$$\phi_{\text{d}} = \Phi_{\text{d}}(\theta_{\text{P}}), \phi_{\text{e}} = \Phi_{\text{e}}(\theta_{\text{P}}), \phi_{\text{f}} = \Phi_{\text{f}}(\theta_{\text{P}}), \phi_{\text{g}} = \Phi_{\text{g}}(\theta_{\text{P}}), \phi_{\text{h}} = \Phi_{\text{h}}(\theta_{\text{P}}) \quad (\text{A.6.4})$$

A.6.5 Stream 5 flow and mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned} q_5 &= Q_5(q_4, q_{10}, q_{11}) \\ \gamma_{\text{a5}} &= \Gamma_{\text{a5}}(\gamma_{\text{a4}}, q_4, q_5), \gamma_{\text{b5}} = \Gamma_{\text{b5}}(\gamma_{\text{b4}}, q_4, q_5), \gamma_{\text{c5}} = \Gamma_{\text{c5}}(\gamma_{\text{c4}}, q_4, q_5) \\ \gamma_{\text{d5}} &= \Gamma_{\text{d5}}(\phi_{\text{d}}, x_{\text{d10}}, q_{10}, q_5), \gamma_{\text{e5}} = \Gamma_{\text{e5}}(\phi_{\text{e}}, x_{\text{e10}}, q_{10}, q_5), \gamma_{\text{f5}} = \Gamma_{\text{f5}}(\phi_{\text{f}}, x_{\text{f10}}, q_{10}, q_5) \\ \gamma_{\text{g5}} &= \Gamma_{\text{g5}}(\phi_{\text{g}}, x_{\text{g10}}, q_{10}, q_5), \gamma_{\text{h5}} = \Gamma_{\text{h5}}(\phi_{\text{h}}, x_{\text{h10}}, q_{10}, q_5) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6.5})$$

A.6.6 Stream 11 mole fractions

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\text{d11}} &= X_{\text{d11}}(x_{\text{d10}}, q_{10}, \gamma_{\text{d5}}, q_5, q_{11}), x_{\text{e11}} = X_{\text{e11}}(x_{\text{e10}}, q_{10}, \gamma_{\text{e5}}, q_5, q_{11}) \\ x_{\text{f11}} &= X_{\text{f11}}(x_{\text{f10}}, q_{10}, \gamma_{\text{f5}}, q_5, q_{11}) \\ x_{\text{g11}} &= X_{\text{g11}}(x_{\text{d11}}, x_{\text{e11}}, x_{\text{f11}}, n_{\text{gP}}, n_{\text{hP}}), x_{\text{h11}} = X_{\text{h11}}(x_{\text{d11}}, x_{\text{e11}}, x_{\text{f11}}, n_{\text{gP}}, n_{\text{hP}}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6.6})$$

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